

Enhancing student engagement in large classes by integrating principles of Universal Design for Learning in a Disability Studies in Education short course at the University of Cape Town

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Abstract

Although promoting inclusive education for all learners has received significant attention internationally, research about learners' engagement in a large class through integration of the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is minimal. The aim of this article is to explore ways to enhance student engagement in large classes which are foregrounded to inclusive teaching and learning in a short course run at the Division of Disability Studies at the University of Cape Town (UCT). A qualitative method was employed for two focus group discussions among learners and tutors. Findings show the strength and weaknesses of the course, technology as a tool for UDL and the value of adding a practical aspect of the course. It was concluded that though there was evidence of the application of the UDL principles which enhanced student engagement, further development of the UDL principle was recommended.

Keywords: *Disability Studies in Education; higher education; large classes; online learning; student engagement; Universal Design for Learning*

1. Introduction

The University of Cape Town (UCT) has been challenged to change ways in which it engages with and responds to students partly because of the student protests (#Rhodes Must Fall and #Fees Must Fall movements) and the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic (Pillay & Kathard, 2015) on teaching and learning. The student movements have highlighted the need for greater educational equity and inclusion, while the pandemic has necessitated the rethinking of traditional in-person pedagogies in relation to digital learning and teaching methods. While UCT remains a contact university, its Vision 2030 states that the traditional residential experience at the university must be combined with elements of blended and online learning to ensure student success including management of large class sizes. This requires the development and enhancement of inclusive and accessible digital learning infrastructure that promotes equity of access, participation, and success. The goal of this article is to describe and evaluate instructional strategies that promote student engagement in large classes and identify easy ways to further implement the principles of UDL that specifically address student engagement.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Inclusive education

Internationally, inclusive education has focused broadly on equitable access to education for students who have been historically excluded, whereas in the United States, it has been focused more narrowly on access to general education curriculum and settings for students with disabilities (Waitoller & Artiles, 2013). Research consistently recommends inclusive education as a best practice for all students (e.g., Baglieri et al., 2011; Ferguson et al., 2019).

In South Africa, the concept of inclusive education has been embraced by the government and there is ample evidence of various white papers, policies, and codes of good practice. For example, in 2001 the Department of Education (DoE) introduced *Education White Paper 6* on Special Needs Education; in 2009 the Department of Social Development published their *Policy on Disability*; in 2015 the Department of Labour produced the *Code of Good Practice on Employment of Persons with Disabilities*; and in 2018 the Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) produced the *Strategic Policy Framework on Disability for the Post School Education and Training System*.

What is less well understood is how these policies and codes of good practice are being implemented in context. In higher education specifically, it is unclear whether decisions about inclusive education are determined by individual student requirements for specially designed instruction in more restrictive settings, or whether other factors such as large class size, limited resources, staff training, and teacher competencies to tailor appropriate supports influence these decisions (Taylor et al., 2020).

One strategy that may assist lecturers in universities to better implement the aspirations of these policies and codes of good practice, is to apply the principles in Universal Design for Learning.

2.2 Universal Design for Learning

Universal Design for Learning (UDL) is an approach to designing education that incorporates flexibility in how information is presented, how students are supported in expressing their developing knowledge and skills, and how students are engaged in the learning environment ([Centre for Applied Special Technology](#) [CAST], 2023). The aim of UDL is to enable students to become more self-directed and expert learners through strategic instructional planning that recognizes and provides for their diverse learning needs. According to Dalton et al. (2019), what distinguishes UDL from differentiated instruction, and other such frameworks is that the planning for learning diversity occurs at the beginning of course design. In this way, existing and potential barriers in the curriculum are identified and mitigated at the outset, while high achievement expectations for all students are enhanced and maintained. This means, a good teacher-learner relationship could be enhanced through UDL. For example, Farrell (2021) posits that good relationships among students creates avenues of engagement which energises the teaching-learning dynamic in the large classroom situation. Fovet (2020) argues that UDL is more urgently required in the large classroom than in other teaching spaces because the inherent demographics of large lectures mean that inclusion needs to be a priority and that solutions must be systematic and effective.

Applying the UDL principles, which have roots in cognitive neuroscience (Rose & Meyer, 2002), is intended to lead to practices where instructors offer students multiple means of representation, engagement, and action and expression:

- Multiple means of representation: For resourceful, knowledgeable learners, present information, and content in different ways. Multiple forms of accessibly designed media are used to communicate course materials.
- Multiple means of engagement: For purposeful, motivated learners, stimulate interest and motivation for learning. In a course, multiple examples broaden the relevance to a diverse student group.
- Multiple means of action and expression: For strategic, goal-directed learners, differentiate the ways that students can express what they know. An assigned course project optimises individual choice and autonomy (Burgstahler et.al, 2021, p. 7).

These principles, which were originally developed for supporting learners with disabilities, are now recognised as important in enhancing and enabling an equal opportunity to learn for all learners (Dalton et al., 2019; UNESCO, 2020). They have also been widely, but unevenly adopted in higher education (e.g. [The INCLUDE Collaboratory](#)¹) where it is recognised that UDL is a practice aimed at the development of all learners, irrespective of whether they face barriers to learning (Burgstahler, 2021) and endeavours to make learning and teaching accessible to the greatest possible range of diversity, rather than catering for the non-existent ‘average learner’ (Baglieri et al., 2011). The proponents of UDL recognise that everyone learns differently and UDL has been promoted as an instructional strategy that can address systemic inequality and discrimination, which may arise from an intersectionality of a diverse range of disadvantages (e.g., racial inequality, gender discrimination, cultural insensitivity, socio-economic barriers, disability) (Rose & Meyer, 2002). The DSE (Disability Studies in Education) short course was not only designed with reference to the UDL framework, but the course content is also centred around it.

Even though UDL is viewed as one approach that can help create more student-centred, responsive curricula which can cater for diversity in the learning community, there can be considerable challenges to its implementation. One challenge is the application of UDL in

¹ <https://include.wp.worc.ac.uk/about-include/>

large classes and mode of assessment. For instance, Karisa (2022) highlighted ideological and systemic challenges that might work against the flexibility envisaged by UDL, such as the focus on standardization of assessments, including the mode of assessment, in contemporary public education systems. The university education system in South Africa is influenced by such standardization expectations, which might leave little space for the flexibility promised by UDL. One way to more easily build in the flexibility and responsiveness envisaged by UDL creators is to focus on student engagement.

3. Methodology

This article is carved from an evaluation study of the 2021 DSE short course cohort at UCT. The qualitative evaluation study used focus group discussion (FGDs) as the main source of data generation. The FGD was in two streams: (1) among five tutors; and (2) with three students. The duration of each of the FGDs was approximately one and a half hours and were guided by open-ended questions. The FGD schedule yielded qualitative data which addressed aspects of course design, engagement, and assessment.

The data from the FGDs was analysed thematically using the six steps advocated by Braun and Clarke (2017) using *Dedoose* for the analysis. The intention is that data from this study will be used for refinement of the DSE short course for subsequent iterations.

4. Description of the Teaching and Learning Context

4.1 Description of the short course

The DSE short course is situated in the Faculty of Health Sciences at UCT. The aim of the short course is to equip participants with the necessary knowledge, skills, and tools to enable them to support learners with disabilities.

We define a short course as a non-credit bearing course aimed at working professionals. The short course has been adapted over the past two years and cohorts have increased from 70 to 200 participants. The high number of 200 students in a cohort emphasised the need to develop UDL as a teaching pedagogy to manage large classes (Fovet, 2020). The first cohort in 2021 attracted students who were training to be Early Childhood Development practitioners, international community-based inclusive development practitioners, and educators. The subsequent cohorts ranged from participants in education, health profession sector and participants providing education and caregiving services for learners requiring support.

The course planning was informed by considerations of accessibility and inclusion. Since the topic of the course was inclusive education, we made every attempt to model an inclusive ethos and practice in our teaching. A central theme of the course was UDL, and here we had to not only teach, but also model UDL. The recognition that education is an issue of social justice was embedded in our discussions of human rights, disability rights, and the need for an intersectoral perspective on inclusion (Nseibo et al., 2023). The teaching and learning strategies using UDL to manage large classes include breaking down of the large classes into smaller cohorts, further reduction of students to smaller tutorial groups (see Figure 1), cooperative learning, group work, working in pairs and others. The next section discusses the course structure and layout and how we integrated the UDL principles in the course.

Figure 1: Cohort breakdown into smaller tutorial groups

4.2 Course structure and layout

The DSE short course was delivered in a hybrid model, utilising synchronous meetings on Zoom and asynchronous content on the digital learning platform. As seen in Figure 1, the course ran for seven weeks, with each week covering a specific topic.

Figure 2: Course layout

Each weekly component of the course included two to three recorded lectures, a weekly online synchronous discussion, a synchronous tutorial meeting, and an online activity (Figure 3).

Key Information

Use the information below to help you manage your workload for this week:

Recommended week dates	27 April - 3 May
Estimated time to complete	10 hours
Week outline	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Lecture 7: Disability and social justice• Lecture 8: The right to education• Online Discussion (Friday)• Tutorial (Monday)• Online Activity (due Tuesday)

Figure 3: Week outline

The synchronous online discussion provided students with a real-time opportunity to engage with the course material. Additionally, the weekly synchronous tutorials allowed for personalised support. Asynchronous activities were incorporated to cater to the diverse needs and preferences of students, as well as to encourage engagement. These activities included watching recorded lecture videos at their own pace, enabling students to revisit the content as needed. Students were also required to provide comments on the weekly content, fostering critical thinking. Also, they were expected to submit reflections in the comment section, allowing for self-assessment. Students were assigned a weekly online activity to consolidate knowledge comprehension. These formal submissions took place in forums, providing a platform for collaborative learning. The course assessment took place at the end of the seven weeks, in the form of a written and oral assignment, requiring students to demonstrate the contextual application of their newly obtained knowledge. Overall, the course layout combined synchronous and asynchronous elements to create an inclusive learning experience to develop "expert learners who are purposeful and motivated, resourceful and knowledgeable and strategic and goal-directed" (CAST, 2017). Examples of how the principles of the UDL framework was applied on the digital platform for this course follow.

4.3 Integrating the principles of UDL in the course

To optimise student engagement, deliberate strategies were adopted across multiple means of representation, multiple means of action and expressions and multiple means of engagement as they all play a role, to a greater or lesser degree, in the overall student experience and how comfortable they are to participate meaningfully in the course. The following sections illustrate how student engagement was encouraged in the course.

Multiple means of representation

Lecturers and presenters focused on the accessibility of available teaching and learning resources bearing in mind the type of impairments students may have in the class (Nseibo et

al., 2022). We found that it became important to offer not just one source, but sources of varying degrees of complexity, level of language, and theoretical density in the large class scenario. As Fovet (2018) suggests, we also found that we need to offer and support multiple pathways into the materials for all diverse students, including those with disabilities in the large classes.

Figures 4 and 5 highlight three specific examples of the implementation of the UDL principle, providing multiple means of representation.

Video representation

Everyone a Changemaker: The Story of Pinelands North
 Estimated time: 7 minutes

Watch the 7 minute YouTube clip on **Everyone a Changemaker: The Story of Pinelands North**. Do second time. Reflect on the roles of the children, teachers, parents and school leadership and how e

Captions on videos

Engaging the child in learning
 Estimated time: 9 minutes

Instructions

- Watch the following video

Video transcriptions

Figure 4: Providing multiple means of representation with video

Cartoon representation

★ Categories of exclusion
 Estimated time: 20 minutes

Using the cartoon below to inform your choices, comment on which categories of exclusion make very few schools accessible to children in South Africa. Read and comment on the contributions of some of your classmates: do you agree or disagree with their categories of exclusion and the reasons. The Covid-19 pandemic has made schooling very different around the world and in South Africa, think about how the pandemic and Covid-19 protocols, which are necessary, also contribute to categories of exclusion. Share your responses in your tutorial group's **Chat Room** (click on Chat Room in the left hand navigation pane, click Change Room at the top of the Chat Room page, and click on your tutorial group's Chat Room).

[Categories of exclusion cartoon.jpg](#)
 Use this link to open the image in a new window.

Figure 5: Providing multiple means of representation with cartoons

To cater to different learning preferences and accommodate individuals with hearing impairments, video captions have been included. These captions enhance understanding by providing a text-based representation of the audio content (Checkpoint 1.1).

We also offered a cartoon option (Figure 4) an alternative to traditional readings or videos. This visual representation appeals to learners who prefer graphical formats and provides an engaging way to access course content (Checkpoint 1.2).

Transcripts of the videos were made available, allowing students to review the content at their own pace or refer to the text version for better comprehension (Checkpoint 1.3). This supports learners who prefer reading or need additional linguistic support and tutors were assigned to a small group to make the large class more intimate.

Multiple means of action and expression

“Integrating action and expression as UDL principle supports instructors as they reshape delivery to give increasing space and freedom to develop an identity as creator of content” (Fovet, 2020, p. 165). Different means of action and expression were exhibited by the incorporation of a variety of assessment methods, and options for students to demonstrate their knowledge and skills via written assessment, online activities, and oral presentations. The tutoring component was very helpful in supporting students on how to use the various digital platforms in smaller groups.

In line with the UDL principle of providing multiple means of action and expression, we have created an inclusive learning environment that enables students to express themselves through various media, utilise different tools for communication, and receive the necessary support to enhance their skills and performance.

Students had access to multiple means of communication, including platforms such as *Zoom* and *MS Teams*. Additionally, students utilised collaborative tools such as discussion forums, group discussions, chat rooms, Padlet boards, and comment sections within the digital platform (Checkpoint 4.1; Checkpoint 5.2).

Figures 6 and 7 provide examples of how this principle is applied, to create diverse pathways for students to navigate the course, express their knowledge, and optimise their learning experience.

The image shows a document titled "Learning Outcomes" with a sub-section "Guidance for goal setting". Below the title, it states "After completing this week, you will be able to:" followed by a bulleted list of 12 learning objectives related to inclusive education and hearing impairment.

Learning Outcomes **Guidance for goal setting**

After completing this week, you will be able to:

- Explore experiences of childhood disability in families.
- Describe an ecosystemic model of inclusive education.
- Explore inclusion and exclusion as connected processes in a mainstream school on its journey to becoming an inclusive school.
- Identify the role of the children, teachers, parents, school leadership and the broader community in the process of creating an inclusive school.
- Reflect on experiences of children who are D/deaf and Hard of hearing in an empathetic way.
- Explore the perspectives of the Deaf community including around terminology and the role that they play in education of learners who are D/deaf and hard of hearing.
- Examine the effect of severe to profound hearing impairment on the deaf children in the classroom.
- Identify barriers to learning experienced by learners who are D/deaf or hard of hearing.
- Apply teaching strategies for inclusive learning in their own educational context for learners who are D/deaf or hard of hearing.
- Explain the importance of human rights and legal issues for learners who are D/deaf and hard of hearing.

Figure 6: Providing multiple means of action and expression with learning outcomes

Support planning and strategy development

Key Information	
Use the information below to help you manage your workload for this week:	
Recommended week dates	8 - 12 November
Estimated time to complete	7 hours
Week outline	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Seminar 13 Preparation (asynchronous)• Seminar 13 (Monday 15:00 - 17:30 via Zoom)<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Lecture 1: Psychosocial aspects of VI• Tutorial (Wednesday 18:00 - 19:00 via Zoom)• Seminar 14 Preparation (asynchronous)• Seminar 14 (Thursday 15:00 - 17:30 via Zoom)<ul style="list-style-type: none">◦ Lecture 1 and 2: Physical impairment: Issues in the education of children with mobility impairments part 1◦ Lecture 3: Physical impairment: Issues in the education of children with mobility impairments part 2• Online Activity (asynchronous via Forums)
Zoom links	Seminar details: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Zoom link: Click here to join the lecture• Meeting ID: 926 9465 1323• Passcode: 930937 Tutorial details: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Zoom link: Click here to join the tutorial• Meeting ID: 747 9690 5569• Passcode: F762IZ
Assessments	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Online Activity: due 14 November (1.5% of course mark)• Final Assignment 2: due 15 November (20% of course mark)

EXAM INSTRUCTIONS: DSE 2021

WRITTEN PRESENTATION

In this course you have explored exclusion of learners with disabilities and how this might be understood through a framework of Disability Studies in Education (DSE). We have examined the barriers that they face within the system and how these barriers may be addressed through curriculum adaptation and appropriate support. In this examination, you will consider the application of DSE in a specific case within the overall inclusive education system. The question is:

How would you adopt a DSE approach in addressing barriers to learning so that learners with disabilities might experience improved access, participation and achievement in education? Choose one of these four vignettes (short stories) of learners with disabilities in order to answer this question.

Vary methods for response

ORAL PRESENTATION

The oral exam will be in two parts:

Part 1:

Figure 7: Providing multiple means of action and expression with weekly information and varying assessment formats

To support students in setting goals (Checkpoint 6.1) we outlined the learning outcomes (Figure 6). Thus, students could gain a clear understanding of what they were expected to achieve throughout the course.

In addition, we recognise the importance of providing flexibility during assessments. By providing students with varying means of assessment, including group work, online activities, written and oral assessment submission, we empowered them to highlight their understanding in a format that aligns with their strengths and preferences (Checkpoint 5.1). Each week's content also included a 'Key Information' table to encourage planning and strategy development (Checkpoint 6.2). By providing students with this essential information, they could effectively manage their time. This strategic approach empowered students to take control of their learning.

Multiple means of engagement

Students were encouraged to set their own learning goals, supported through an open line of communication with the tutor and course convenor. Students were advised to communicate any challenges they were experiencing, and concessions were made where appropriate.

Recognising that students possess diverse interests, motivations, and preferences for engagement, we have adopted a range of strategies to cater for their needs. Examples of these strategies are illustrated in Figures 8 and 9.

★ Activity: Case study on Jenna-Lee

Estimated time: 1 hour

For this activity, download the Word document linked below, which contains the story of Jenna-Lee. The document also includes four questions for you to respond to. Respond to the questions in the document and then copy and paste the questions and your answers into a conversation in the Forum. The Forum link is also added below. Read and comment on the responses of two of your peers.

 Case study on Jenna Lee.docx

 Week 4: Case study of Jenna-Lee

Formal discussion forum

★ Reflection

Think of an example of where you think justice as concerns the right to education has not been done. Share your example using the Comment button below.

The screenshot shows a forum interface with several comments. At the top, there are buttons to 'See All 8 comments ...' and 'See All 8 new comments ...'. Below are five comment entries, each with a date (20-Sep-2022 or 27-Sep-2022), a status icon (red X or green checkmark), and a comment icon. The comments discuss issues like education for disabled children, government accountability, and disability inclusion. At the bottom, there is an 'Add Comment' button.

Informal chat with
'Comment' tool

Figure 8: Providing multiple means of engagement with communication tools

The screenshot shows a seminar page titled 'Seminar 9'. A large box labeled 'Synchronous engagement' is overlaid on the page. Below the title, there are two lecture sections: 'Lecture 1' and 'Lecture 2', each with presenter, date, time, and topic information. To the right, there is a 'Week 2 Tutorial' section with dates and times. At the bottom, there is a 'Small group tutorials' section.

Synchronous online lectures

Figure 9: Providing multiple means of engagement synchronously

Formal online discussions using the forum tool on the digital platform fostered collaboration among students (Checkpoint 8.3). Synchronous online meetings were structured to cater for those who thrive on routine and prefer real-time instruction (Checkpoint 7.1). Small group tutorial sessions provided personalised attention and support (Checkpoint 7.3; Checkpoint 8.3). Furthermore, an informal chat space (chat room) on the digital platform facilitated spontaneous conversations, appealing to students who find such spontaneity engaging (Checkpoint 7.1).

Teaching large cohorts exposes educators and students to diverse backgrounds and perspectives, enhancing the learning environment. However, accommodating poses challenges. For instance, online discussion forums enable active participation and engagement among students, but providing individual feedback to large cohorts can be time-consuming. One strategy we employed to reduce the workload was to let students engage in tutorial group-specific forums. This meant that each tutorial group would have its own discussion forum to post in, with the allocated tutor providing feedback. This allowed tutors to equally share the workload, without excluding any student - consequently building trust with students by letting them feel heard, and in turn promoting engagement.

5. Reflection on Practice

While we found that *multiple means of representation* and *multiple means of action and expression* played an essential role, it became evident that *multiple means of engagement* (Guidelines 7, 8 & 9) in a large online class was imperative to students' access, participation, and success.

The main challenge in large classes is student engagement. When students found themselves disoriented due to navigating our learning management system, "loadshedding" or connectivity issues which is often an issue with large online classes, they would withdraw and as a result feel isolated or excluded. In such circumstances tutors, tutorial groups and group work served as a "lifeline" for students. Tutors consistently reached out to students who were not participating in activities. They would contact them via email, WhatsApp or even call them. Group work worked well in ensuring students engaged in activities as students would support one another with the workload, and the expectation to contribute motivated students to participate.

Guideline 7: Providing options for recruiting interest

Students were given the option to work in groups or individually. Most students chose to work in groups. Students were also given autonomy over how to present their assignments. For example, written and oral assessments (20-minute online presentation with 5 minutes for questions and answers (Q&A) or a short video with a 10-minute online Q&A session). All the assessment activities related to their own experience and context were designed in the hope that application of their learning would enhance their ability to be more inclusive in their teaching practice. Tutors provided technical assistance, guidance and availed themselves for assessments.

Guideline 8: Providing options for sustaining effort and persistence

Tutors, convenor and presenters played a critical role in creating a supportive and accepting environment. A sense of community was fostered even though it was still emerging (Farrell, 2021). Tutors used every opportunity to ensure students felt a sense of belonging, value, and support. This encourages student effort and persistence and suggests what other educators might choose to implement and replicate in their educational contexts. In addition, learning objectives were explicitly stated at each level and learning was scaffolded through preparatory and practice activities (Nseibo et al., 2023).

Guideline 9: Providing options for self-regulation

Tutors, the convenor and presenters played a critical role in creating a supportive and accepting environment. Many students felt overwhelmed by the workload and experienced health issues. In response to their concerns, tutors and the convenor responded to students where possible by providing other options and considering their recommendations. For

example, being open to discussions on adjusted submission dates and adding checklists for future cohorts. Rubrics and prompts were provided to students, and reflective tasks were encouraged.

6. Conclusion

While online courses offer students the opportunity to participate in higher education, this format could create barriers for the very students who need the option of distance learning as the promise that technology holds for accessibility also contains the possibility of exclusion and isolation of students.

An important course element to mitigating the feeling of isolation is the creation of supportive communities for students (Farrell, 2021). Creating a community of practice through small group tutorial systems and peer interactions was partly what was required to create a sense of belonging and encouraging social presence and student engagement in a large class context, especially in an online space. Utilising digital collaborative tools for discussions in tutorial groups were helpful to facilitate peer engagement online in instances where real-time interaction between the entire cohort could be time-consuming. This strategy, and other examples mentioned previously, may be useful for enhancing engagement in large classes, whether presented online, hybrid or face-to-face. Contextualising the curriculum through pedagogical practices such as facilitating sessions rather than lecturing and deliberately creating opportunities for students to share their tacit knowledge are all crucial elements to creating a course which sets out to accommodate the needs of non-traditional students in higher education (Nseibo et al., 2023).

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